

The Durga Puja Mystery

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Keywords

Culture, Durga Puja, History, Indian Festival Culture, Intercultural Communication, Religion, South Asian Studies

Figure 1. Screenshot from *The Durga Puja Mystery* (Zeiler & Chakrabarti). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

The educational video game *The Durga Puja Mystery* (see Figure 1) introduces Indian festival culture by focusing on the popular and widespread Hindu festival Durga Puja. Today, Durga Puja is not only widely celebrated in India but is also a significant event for global Indian communities (e.g., Guha-Thakurta, 2015; Zeiler, 2025). The game is a third-person 3D adventure filled with mystery, featuring educational puzzles, riddles, and tasks. It takes place in and around a majestic heritage mansion near Kolkata, India, during Durga Puja, naturally!

The game is part of a set of two educational video games at the festival, developed specifically for university teaching. *The Durga Puja Mystery* (2020) and *Durga Puja Beyond Borders* (2021) can be played in combination or as stand-alone games, depending on the player's interest.

Facts

Release date:	2020
Developer:	Collaboration between Xenia Zeiler, University of Helsinki, Finland, and Satyajit Chakrabarti, Flying Robot Studios, Kolkata, India
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	60–120 minutes, depending on the options the player chooses
Languages:	English
Environment:	Windows PC
Material:	The game is downloadable from a public website that additionally offers game-accompanying academic context information on the festival Durga Puja (two academic lectures, one academic blog post, and one documentary), produced specifically for the two educational video games on Durga Puja, see https://blogs.helsinki.fi/durgapuja-the-videogame/
Price:	Fully open access and free of charge, as the game development was fully funded by the University of Helsinki

Resonance & Criticism

The Durga Puja Mystery was selected as a finalist in the Finnish Hacking Higher Education contest 2020 (see <https://blogs.helsinki.fi/durgapuja-the-videogame/hacking-higher-education-finland-2020-finalist/>). Collected voluntary student feedback praised the game's innovative, playful approach to learning about the festival. Additionally, the game has gained international awareness among university teachers.

Sample course titles in which the game has been used so far include “Globalization, Global Communities, and Transcultural Encounters”, “Who has got the Power? Communicating and Negotiating Authority and Identity in Indian Festival Cultures,” and “Identities and Digital Networks of Migrant Communities”.

Game Principle & Process

As mentioned above, The Durga Puja Mystery is an educational video game developed to introduce selected core aspects of Indian culture and society by using the festival of Durga Puja as a case study.

In this game, the player plays as Laura, a Finnish student who is visiting India for the first time. She has been invited by her Indian friend Vani to celebrate Durga Puja with her and her family. Vani takes Laura to her ancestral home, where the festival of Durga Puja is about to begin. Both arrive at the majestic house expecting a fun-filled and educational time, only to find that all the celebrations are on hold. The ancestral metal statue of the goddess Durga, which is a key part of the celebration, is missing. At the request of the lady of the house, Vani's aunt,

Laura takes on the task of finding the statue. She gains more profound insights into and knowledge of the festival's history, mythological contexts, iconography, and modes of worship and celebration – and employs this new knowledge and her investigative skills to find the statue. As she progresses, the mystery deepens.

Educational games have several specific pedagogical characteristics and requirements that set them apart from non-educational games (as noted as early as 2007; see, e.g., Mishra & Foster, 2007). They include, but are not limited to, acknowledging and accepting that they can, and at times must be rather text-heavy and that there is a constant need to balance the 'learning' and the 'play' experiences – and to combine these two skillfully. This is an ongoing challenge, especially for educational games designed for humanities disciplines. One of our solutions that helped bring together the play and the learning experiences was implementing an academic library into the gameplay of *The Durga Puja Mystery* and supporting the learning process initiated by the game through an accompanying website with academic context information.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The Durga Puja Mystery has an overall objective, as well as more specific and detailed learning subgoals. The primary, overarching goal is to provide students and interested general audiences with access to knowledge of the Durga Puja festival—including its complex history, celebratory practices, and global spread—in a playful yet academically sound way. The game's sub-goals include specific classroom usability across a variety of courses suited to the academic disciplines of South Asian studies, Asian studies, religious studies, and area and cultural studies.

Throughout gameplay, the player is tasked with educational activities and investigative puzzles, gradually learning about Durga Puja. That is, the player collects various items, including reference books, texts, and images, that can help with the investigation and play a key part in winning the game. Simultaneously, and as is characteristic of educational games, these items introduce the player to various key themes related to Durga Puja and support the player in their educational and academic quest. They are selected with the aim of conveying information about and inspiring further interest in Indian culture.

That is, the game takes an open approach to learning objectives, aiming to inform and spark interest in the selected theme. It does not use specific, quantifiable learning tasks and/or objectives because it does not target quantifiable learning outcomes. Instead, one of the game's main objectives is to allow players to have their own experiences, in addition to content knowledge about Durga Puja. For example, the choice of location, a heritage mansion and surrounding garden park, was a conscious attempt to boost the players/students' immersion experience. This setting requires much walking during gameplay and allows the player/student to explore, at their chosen pace, specific cultural aesthetics we tried to capture, such as various architectural styles and the native landscape (Zeiler, 2025).

The Durga Puja Mystery is easy to use on Windows PC or laptop with the required system requirements (<https://blogs.helsinki.fi/durgapuja-the-videogame/play/>). After a free download, the game can be played immediately. All practical instructions, as well as game-accompanying academic content that can support the player during gameplay are free of charge and easily accessible. This design reflects the fact that using an educational video game in classroom settings should always be supported by other learning activities, such as assigned academic readings on the game's content matter, group discussions, and the use of different media formats. As this is a single-player game, it is even more advisable to embed it in collaborative class discussions and in further information sources and learning activities on the theme.

Effectiveness

A postmortem of the game by Zeiler & Chakraborti (2024) further investigated the pros and cons of The Durga Puja Mystery (and of the second game in the mentioned duo, Durga Puja Beyond Borders, 2021). This report discusses reflections and assessments on the effectiveness, successes, and challenges in both the development process and the final game product. It builds on student feedback to evaluate how the game was received as a learning material. This voluntary student feedback, collected over several courses where the game was an assignment and including short statements as well as several page-long game reviews, ascertains that the game succeeded in enhancing the learning experience by utilizing components such as soundscapes, colors, narrative structures, and the overall interactive element of video games to create an extended level of immersion into the theme (e.g., Blumberg & Blumberg, 2014; Mayer, 2014).

This report reiterates the specific pedagogical characteristics and requirements that set educational games apart from non-educational games. They include, but are not limited to, acknowledging and accepting that such games can and, at times, must be rather text-heavy, and that there is a constant need to balance the 'learning' and the 'play' experiences. This is an ongoing challenge to date, especially for educational games designed for humanities disciplines.

For The Durga Puja Mystery, one of our solutions to bring together the play and the learning experiences was to integrate an academic library into the gameplay and to support the learning process initiated by the games through the accompanying website, providing academic context information.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game is most effectively and smoothly played when the specified PC/laptop system requirements (including a minimum Intel Core 2 Duo 3.0 GHz or AMD Athlon 64 X2 6400+ 3.2 GHz, and a graphics card minimum NVIDIA® GeForce® GT 600 or AMD Radeon™ equivalent) are met. At the moment, the game must still be downloaded and installed to play. We actively

continue to seek funding to improve this and other technical issues and hope to offer a browser-based solution in the future.

Because educational games on complex cultural and social themes will likely always require extended text (dialogue, instructions, etc.), it is challenging to find a workable balance between integrating text and allowing for more play- and story-driven elements. This should be communicated to students before playing.

Reviewer(s): Walter Dettling, Lucian Alikhani

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